

D.3.1 Strategy and guidelines for setup the local co-creation labs in form of Community of Practice

Consortium

CIVITTA

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CoP(s)	Community(ies) of Practice
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
ML	Mutual Learning
MoC	Memorandum of Cooperation
NGO(s)	Non-governmental organization(s)
VET	Vocational education and training

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Executive Summary

This document titled “**D3.1: Report on strategy and guidelines for setup the local co-creation labs in form of Community of Practice**”, has been elaborated as a deliverable of **BioGov.net** describing the approach followed for the development of BioGov.net’ community of practice framework. The project aims at supporting the establishment of the innovative governance model in bioeconomy training and skills development to achieve better-informed decision -making processes, social engagement of all actors and uptake of sustainable innovations in bioeconomy. In this context, BioGov.net entails the creation of eight regional and one European network of diverse stakeholders within the bioeconomy sector to participate and support the design, development, testing, validation and roll-out of the BioGov.net guidelines in training and upskilling.

To produce meaningful and demand-driven results, tools and practical knowledge, BioGov.net will establish 8 Communities of Practice (CoP) in different countries, namely Estonia, Greece, Portugal, Slovakia, Italy, Czechia, Netherlands, Germany.

With our Community of Practice approach framework in place, our target is to directly engage 240 actors in the CoPs in total, approximately 30 members in each BioGov.net country/local CoP. The Deliverable will also propose a dedicated strategy for the inclusion of marginalised groups.

CoP will comprise of a broad range of bioeconomy stakeholders (producers, consumers, academics, policy makers, NGOs, etc.) who will be engaged in key project activities throughout the project. BioGov.net shall ensure inclusiveness and engagement of all actors, moreover of marginalized groups, such as: women, ethnic and religious minorities, migrants and refugees, the LGBTIQ community, disabled persons, youth and the elderly, etc. with special attention to elements of art and addressing the needs of people from marginalized, disadvantaged or vulnerable groups.

Members of the CoP will be provided with the opportunity to express their interests and perspectives and shape the development of the BioGov.net training and educational framework in bioeconomy to better serve their needs. At the same time, CoP will act as a bridge between the local and the international perspectives.

To successfully establish and operate the Communities of Practice framework, BioGov.net has elaborated a tailored methodology to ensure comparable but well-adjusted to local contexts results from regional CoPs. The mission of the CoPs, as well as the expected structure and expected contribution of their members, has been defined to aid BioGov.net consortium in producing guidelines and training/mentoring frameworks in bioeconomy sector, following a balanced participation of actors in adult learning, skill development, inclusion of bio-systems, active communities, policy makers, citizens and researchers. A common protocol for the identification and selection of the CoP members has been set, as a guide for consortium partners leading a CoP to efficiently establish these structures. Moreover, guidelines for inviting members and managing their inclusion as well as potential conflicts of interest that may arise during project activities, are also defined. The rights and duties of members, their expected role, terms of participation as well as a timeline of their participation in the CoP have been developed to promote clear communication among partners and stakeholders. The recruitment process is well under way and all Community of Practice structures will be open for new members throughout the project.

1 Introduction

BioGov.net aims at establishing an innovative governance model in bioeconomy training and skills development, to achieve better informed decision-making processes, social engagement and sustainable innovation on bioeconomy sector. BioGov.net specific objective is to provide validated guidelines for set up of the regional bioeconomy training and mentoring frameworks based on case studies from eight EU regions. This will be achieved by engaging 10 experienced partners to mobilize local resources and stakeholders from Estonia, Italy, the Netherlands, Greece, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Portugal and Germany.

A dedicated **protocol for the BioGov.net CoP** has been elaborated to set out the framework as well as the approach to be followed for setting up and running these Community of Practice structures, ensuring the effective engagement of stakeholders.

The current report presents the protocols for the CoP and is comprised of 5 distinct chapters:

- **Chapter 1** provides introductory information about the BioGov.net project and the context in which this report has been elaborated.
- **Chapter 2** describes the objectives of BioGov.net Community of Practice approach as well as the key project targets pertaining to stakeholder engagement in the activities of BioGov.net.
- **Chapter 3** sets out the framework of the CoP, outlines the approach for members' selection and engagement, the status of member recruitment as well as CoP management.
- **Chapter 4** outlines the specific activities in which CoP members will participate throughout the project implementation.
- **Chapter 5** concludes on the next steps of the Communities of Practice.

Last but not least, the Annexes of this report include the tools provided for engaging the CoP members: Invitation letter from the CoP Leader to be used by partners when inviting prospective members to be engaged in the CoP (Annex I); Terms of Reference for the CoP Members (Annex II); Templates for the Declaration of Acceptance used for CoP members (Annex III); The Memorandum of Cooperation (MoC), as an alternative means of cooperation scheme, in case a stakeholder is reluctant in signing a Declaration of Acceptance (Annex IV); The Informed Consent Form that refers to personal data exploitation (Annex V) and finally the template with the structure of the Stakeholder Matrix which partners will use, for their convenience, to monitor the engagement of stakeholders in the CoP as it evolves (Annex VI).

2 Objectives and key targets

The **overarching aim** of this report is to describe our approach for the development of BioGov.net Communities of Practice framework and establish a common protocol that will guide consortium partners through the whole process of identifying, recruiting, and engaging relevant bioeconomy actors in the activities of the project.

Specific objectives of this report are to:

- Describe the Community of Practice structures that will operate in the frame of BioGov.net, namely the Community of Practice (CoP), along with their expected structure, mission and the “rights and duties” of members.
- Elaborate guidelines on how partners can approach the selection, initial contact and engagement of stakeholders to regional CoPs, as well as principles for fostering their inclusiveness.
- Define the main activities in which members of each CoP will participate along the process of identifying, assessing, and validating the BioGov.net framework as well as in the process of rolling out and replicating results at a national and pan-European level in terms of policies.

The BioGov.net project aims to involve approximately 240 stakeholders of the bioeconomy sector through direct stakeholder engagement and participation in its activities including designathons (alternatively focus groups and co-creation workshops)¹, co-design workshops and policy workshops. More specifically, this means approximately thirty regional actors expected to participate in each focal region of the project.

¹ BioGov.net Grant Agreement is under amendment process by the time D3.1 is delivered. Each designathon may be substituted alternatively by a focus group and a co-creation workshop)

3 Community of Practice framework

The Community of Practice framework of BioGov.net foresees the creation of distinct structure (i.e. groups of stakeholders playing a key role in the bioeconomy sector) on the basis of geographical scope and expected contribution to the project. The following sections of this chapter provide further details about the CoP, their mission and expected structure.

3.1 Community of Practice definition

Communities of Practice (CoP) are regional networks of stakeholders coming from across the entire value chain of the bioeconomy sector as well as researchers in each region, policy makers, groups representing civil society, actors involved in adult learning, retraining and skills' development, bio-system representatives (industries, SMEs), active communities (national cultural and natural heritage keepers, artists, designers, professionals' associations), cultural and creative sectors but also citizen's organisations and marginalized groups, reaching a balanced participation. One CoP will be established in each of the project's 8 participating regions, hereafter referred to as "Regions", with diverse profiles of bioeconomy actors. Each CoP is led by a consortium partner, the CoP Leader and each country focuses on supporting on mobilizing local resources and stakeholders to establish innovative governance models on bioeconomy. More information on the management and operation of CoP are provided in Section 3.6 of this report.

The CoPs should gather representatives from the quadruple helix, formulating a network of approximately 30 members in each one of the 8 BioGov.net partner countries, thus gathering 240 stakeholders in total. The members of each CoP will be involved in the discussion and workshops, will share knowledge and lastly exchange experience (peer to peer dialogue). The member's participation is on a voluntary basis.

The goal of the CoP is to enhance the quality, offer and diversify of Bioeconomy actions and processes for training and skills enhancement by bringing relevant actors in contact with each other, both virtually and face to face. Together, they form a professional network, to:

- Develop and evaluate training materials, tools, strategies, and innovative concepts
- Share experiences and good practices among actors coming from different sectors and regional perspectives
- Consult with industry and stakeholders about skills demands in the market and expected outcomes
- Offer their feedback on guidelines developed in the context of BioGov.net and policy recommendations needed

The combined effort of professionals working together on related goals is expected to enhance participatory decision making, effective guidelines development and inclusive methods of all bioeconomy value chain stakeholders.

3.1.1 Which are the CoPs of BioGov.net and where will they be set up?

The table below presents the countries and the partner assigned as the CoP Leader.

Table 1 Partner Regions & CoP Leaders

Region	CoP Leader
Greece (whole country)	Q-PLAN
Estonia (whole country)	CE
North Region, Portugal	LOBA
Zilina region, Slovakia	PC
Italy (whole country)	FVA in collaboration with UNIBO
Czech Republic (whole country)	ART
Southwest Netherlands	AVANS
Rhenish mining area (<i>Rheinisches Revier</i>) Germany	WILA-Wissenschaftsladen Bonn

3.1.2 Mission

CoP's mission is to aid BioGov.net consortium in producing guidelines and training/mentoring frameworks in bioeconomy sector. More specifically the mission of CoP members is to:

- Provide the consortium with relevant information that will be used to create practical and easily understandable knowledge and tools, bridging the gap between practitioners and researchers, based on successful case studies and good practices.
- Define regional needs and expectations, local feedstock availabilities and uses, and needs for new skills required.
- Build guidelines of training for skill development
- Facilitate the cross-fertilization among regions through exchange of good practices.

3.2 Expected structure

In each one of the 8 BioGov.net partner countries, a group of (approximately) 30 stakeholders (240 in total in project level), will be identified to recruit the respective regional CoP covering the entire spectrum of the quadruple helix. The groups of actors to be invited as well as an indicative structure for each CoP are presented in the following table. The aim is to reach a balanced participation of actors in each regional CoP.

Table 2 Expected structure for Community of Practice

Stakeholder Groups	Needs & Roles	Indicative Membership
<p><i>Research and higher educational organizations</i></p>	<p>Needs:</p> <p>i) adopt research and educational curricula that empower bioeconomy, ii) better feedback loops</p> <p>Role:</p> <p>provide adequate information, guidelines and network that respond to the needs of bio-systems in each region and contribute to the transition to bioeconomy. Also provide information on existing training opportunities offered in the field of bioeconomy</p>	<p>4</p>
<p><i>Vocational education organizations (VET)</i></p>	<p>Needs:</p> <p>i) adopt adult training and mentoring programmes that empower bioeconomy, ii) better feedback loops on the effectiveness of training offers</p> <p>Role:</p> <p>provide transferable training guidelines based on bio-communities needs</p>	<p>4</p>
<p><i>Industry</i></p>	<p>Needs:</p> <p>i) information regarding local, regional, and EU economic potentialities and barriers, iii) employees with improved skills, iv) competitive products, v) support on transition to be more sustainable in manufacturing</p> <p>Role:</p> <p>provide adequate information on the framework conditions (market, economy trends, entrepreneurial culture, existing human capital etc) and on the potential or the barriers of the industry to provide or enable access to tailored training, access to industry sector networks</p>	<p>3</p>

Stakeholder Groups	Needs & Roles	Indicative Membership
<p><i>Businesses (SMEs)</i></p>	<p>Needs: i) flexible training programmes, ii) development of existing or new skills, iii) exploitation of new technologies, iv) exploration of new markets, v) economic growth and support on transition to sustainable manufacturing, vi) skilled employees</p> <p>Role: develop training on skills enhancement on bio-economy and skills leading to novel business models or novel job descriptions</p>	<p>4</p>
<p><i>Policy-Makers & Administration</i></p>	<p>Needs: i) informed decision making for improved education and training on bio-economy, ii) enabling policy measures for bioeconomic transformation, iii) minimization of potential risks and conflicts, iv) sufficient knowledge to make the case for preference of local Bio-based products in public procurement procedures</p> <p>Role: provide information regarding enablers for transformation which needs to be supported by adequate training offers on knowledge and skills needed for transformation processes, opportunities for intergovernmental, multidisciplinary cooperation and access to CoP, support stakeholder's networks towards bioeconomy transition</p>	<p>4</p>
<p><i>NGOs & marginalized groups</i></p>	<p>Needs: i) development of skills leading to the novel governance models and related social warranties, ii) inclusion of marginalized people in training opportunities</p> <p>Role: have a voice in knowledge/ training needed and skills needed to actively contribute to transition processes, enhance marginalized people to master their lives and face the future with confidence</p>	<p>4</p>

Stakeholder Groups	Needs & Roles	Indicative Membership
<p><i>Active Communities, Cultural and creative industries (C.C.Is)</i></p>	<p>Needs:</p> <p>Integration of the opportunities created by the human-centric principles, offered by art, culture and (eco)-design, in respect to the bio-based feedstocks, including traditional and novel biological materials.</p> <p>Role:</p> <p>produce state-of-art guidelines for bioeconomy training and mentoring responsive to the needs of bio-systems and provide the ability to see opportunities from human-centric principles, offered by art, culture and (eco)-design, in respect to the bio-based feedstocks</p>	<p>4</p>
<p><i>Citizens & Wider Society</i></p>	<p>Needs:</p> <p>i) alternatives to switch to socially and environmentally responsible behaviour within their choices, ii) inclusion of marginalized groups in bioeconomy uptake</p> <p>Role:</p> <p>adopt more environmentally friendly habits, increase visibility of bio-based alternatives, take part in formulating more informed decision making and active contribution to local, regional or national transformation processes towards sustainable consumption (based on choices of bioeconomy products). Choosing biobased solutions or biobased products in daily life, will influence more people to follow a greener behaviour.</p>	<p>3</p>

The members distribution within each CoP, as presented in the table above is indicative and may vary among regions to better represent specificities of the bioeconomy ecosystems, focal sectors and actors of these regions in line with the selection criteria outlined in Section 3.3.

3.3 Stakeholder identification process and methods

3.3.1 Selection process

A common process is suggested to be followed in each CoP for selecting its members. A straightforward five-step procedure is presented in the figure below, outlining all steps from the initial identification of stakeholders to their invitation to join the CoP and their involvement in relevant project activities. CoP Leaders are responsible for the selection of stakeholders in the CoP of their respective Region/Country (CoP Leaders are presented in Section 3.6).

Figure 1: Selection process of CoPs members

The engagement of the stakeholders in the regional CoPs may not be a one-off procedure. This means that the total goal of 30 stakeholders involved may not be achieved right from the first exploration of members. The identification and engagement of stakeholder may evolve alongside with the project development and progress.

In the next section, the criteria that will be used for the selection of stakeholders to be included in CoP are presented along with the rationale for their use.

3.3.2 Selection criteria

The criteria applied for selecting CoP members, in line with their mission and expected structure of each CoP, capture a broad range of dimensions regarding the characteristics that members should possess to ensure effective participation in CoP activities. Along these lines, the following table summarises the selection criteria to be followed when assessing possible CoP members, along with the justification for their inclusion.

Table 3 Selection criteria and rationale for criteria inclusion

No.	Selection criterion	Rationale for criterion inclusion
1	Interest	Individuals with high interest in the bioeconomy sector will ensure that they are driven to participate and help the project produce meaningful results with significant added value for their users.
2	Availability	Individuals that have the available time required to participate will enable partners to smoothly organise and execute project activities with higher participation rates that will result in a higher probability that their targets are achieved.

No.	Selection criterion	Rationale for criterion inclusion
3	Relevance	The stakeholders' relevance to the scope and objectives of the project is necessary to keep the activities of CoP focused and will ensure that their members can effectively contribute to the production of relevant project outputs.
4	Appropriateness	The consortium will make sure that members selected to participate in the CoP are appropriate to their scope thus avoiding barriers or involvement in activities that may cause them unnecessary inconvenience.
5	Representativeness	A balanced representation of perspectives within and across stakeholder groups is key for the CoP to collect the representative insights required to inform design, development, and fine-tuning, thus addressing diverse needs.
6	Willingness	Motivated individuals willing to contribute with their knowledge and experience will promote success of CoP activities and will be more prone to help disseminate the project's tools and knowledge, facilitating exploitation and sustainability.
7	Gender	The tools to be developed by BioGov.net should reflect the interests and needs of all genders.
8	Age	Potential stakeholders should not be overlooked on the basis of age. The knowledge and tools produced by BioGov.net will be more relevant and therefore will have more practical value if age disparities of prospective users are taken into account.

The following section outlines guidelines for partners to establish and maintain contact with stakeholders as well as principles for fostering inclusion and effective engagement in CoP.

3.4 Guidelines for contact and engagement

3.4.1 Contact guidelines

This section outlines a set of contact guidelines for the initial and subsequent communications of partners with members of the CoP to ensure effective collaboration with them during the project.

Dedicated communication materials have been prepared to facilitate the first contact of partners with CoP members and to ensure that stakeholders have sufficient information concerning their participation and role in BioGov.net Community of Practice structures and their activities. In particular, the following documents have been produced:

- **Official Invitation letter** from the CoP Leader to accompany the initial communication of consortium partners with selected stakeholders (Annex I).
- **Terms of Reference**, providing meaningful information about BioGov.net and the activities in which CoP members are included, as well as their expected contribution and conditions pertaining to their membership (Annex II).
- **Declaration of Acceptance**, to be signed by each one of the invited stakeholders evidencing the fact that they agree with the terms and conditions of their participation in the respective CoP and that they are willing to be a member of the regional Community of Practice structure (Annex III).
- **MEMORANDUM OF COOPERATION (MoC)**, as an alternative means of cooperation scheme, in case a stakeholder is not convinced in signing a declaration. The MoC may be signed between the CoP Leader and one or more

involved parties in the bioeconomy sector to be part of the Community of Practice (CoP) (Annex IV).

- **Informed Consent Form**, with detailed description on how BioGov.net handles personal data following GDPR rules (Annex V).
- **Stakeholder matrix**, which partners may use, for their convenience, to monitor the engagement of stakeholders in the CoP (Annex VI).

In case a stakeholder is not willing to originally sign neither the Declaration of Acceptance nor a MoC, but still wants to participate in the regional CoP, a Google Form to register to the local CoP is highly recommended as a more user-friendly tool, that puts less pressure to the stakeholders. The Google Form should be created by a CoP leader (if necessary) since he /she is responsible for collecting personal data of local stakeholders, not forgetting also to ask for their consent on using their data (GDPR).

Table 4 Guidelines for contacting CoP members

Stage	Contact guidelines
<p>Initial contact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The initial contact with prospective members of each CoP should be carried out by the respective CoP Leaders. • All initial contact should be accompanied by the communication material prepared to this end (Terms of Reference, Declaration of Acceptance, official invitation letter. The project Brochure is highly recommended to accompany initial contacts, too). • Employ a language that will be easily understood by the stakeholders and ensure that they comprehend the rights and duties implied by their participation. Along these lines, all partners are free to translate the given guidelines and templates in local language if this may better serve local communication with stakeholders. • Further communication via e-mail or teleconference is encouraged in order to reply to any questions or provide clarifications. • Stakeholders who accept to join a CoP, should sign the Declaration of Acceptance or a MoC.
<p>Subsequent communications</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partners managing a CoP should handle/liaise all communications with members of these structures. • CoP members should be properly and timely informed to participate in upcoming project activities (e.g., interviews, surveys, focus groups, events). • CoP Leaders should ensure that no member is overloaded with unneeded information about any task at hand. • Prior to contacting members for a specific action, necessary material and briefings should be prepared to inform participants about the scope of the activity and their expected role.

On top of these contact guidelines, guiding principles for engagement and inclusion of stakeholders in CoP activities have also been elaborated and presented in the following sections.

3.4.2 Guiding principles for engagement

The following table presents an indicative overview of key potential interests and barriers of key stakeholder groups of BioGov.net that may arise during their engagement in the project along with a set of proposed principles on how to effectively manage their engagement.

Table 5: Main interests, barriers, and engagement principles for key stakeholder groups

Stakeholder groups	Potential interests and barriers that may arise during their engagement	Principles for managing their engagement
<i>Academia and Research</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The potential gap between educational curricula and the missing training opportunities may disincentivize engagement in project activities • Emphasis on dissemination of research outputs may pose barriers to the protection of intellectual property of the BioGov.net partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Showcase ways of integrating stakeholders needs in research, engagement and learning • Emphasis on scientific contributions of the project in open access journals and knowledge dissemination channels • Emphasis on the orientation of the project's outputs and tools towards providing practical support to users • Focus on building trust among stakeholder groups and creating a shared vision among them
<i>Vocational Education Organisations (VET)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Little knowledge on how vocational programmes in Bio-Economy can pay off in the labour market • Ageing workforces in VET institutions cannot follow contemporary trends towards bioeconomy • Not close collaboration and exchange between VET institutions and industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go beyond traditional forms of one-time feedback, to more multi-directional, collaborative communication strategies in order to develop trust between the CoP Initiative and the VET Organisations
<i>Biobased Industry & Businesses (SMEs)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest for clear business benefits stemming from involvement in project activities and utilisation of the BioGov.net guidelines • Interest in workforce with relevant skills and education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on building trust among stakeholder groups and creating a shared vision among them • Emphasis on demonstrating the business benefits of the

Stakeholder groups	Potential interests and barriers that may arise during their engagement	Principles for managing their engagement
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fear of losing possible competitive advantage in the local market due to disclosure of business information • Interest in sustainable solutions with respect to supporting local businesses, consumers and local produce 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BioGov.net guidelines and value propositions
<i>Policy Makers & Administration</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest in building suitable incentives and support measures for bioeconomic transformation and minimize potential risks • Potential bureaucratic and relatively slow decision-making processes. • Need for sufficient knowledge to make the case for preference of local Bio-based products in public procurement procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasis on BioGov.net tools designed for training policy makers and Bio-products procurers • Focus on the need to offer evidence-based policy recommendations pinpointing the impact of the adoption of Bio-friendly policies
<i>Active Communities, cultural and creative industries, Artists and NGOs for marginalized groups</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential conflict with businesses on the trade-off between prioritising business gains vs produce creative, artistic and design more expensive products • Missing educational projects or opportunities for marginalized groups to provide career counselling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative activities, including art to inspire citizens or end users • Emphasis on evidence-based impact of the project on supporting these groups
<i>Citizens & wider society</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest in quality Biobased products with affordable prices. • Need for easy access to transparent information on product identity, production methods and origin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasis on economic, societal and environmental benefits stemming from the project's outputs and tools. • Use of simple and straightforward language understood by wider society. • Focus on building trust among society groups and creating a shared vision among them

3.4.2.1 Marginalized, disadvantaged and minority groups – a definition

There is no definition of marginalized communities within the EU legislative framework. It is up to individual Member States to identify which groups they consider to be marginalized based on their own criteria. People can be marginalized in many ways, with marginalisation

embracing factors such as material deprivation, inadequate housing, low educational levels, high unemployment, poor health as well as discrimination and prejudice.²

If needed to give a definition on marginalized, disadvantaged, and minority groups, it could be “different groups and communities of people within a given culture, context and history at risk of being subjected to multiple discrimination due to the interplay of different personal characteristics or grounds, such as sex, gender, age, ethnicity, religion or belief, health status, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, education or income, or living in various geographic localities”³.

Social exclusion or social marginalisation is the social disadvantage and relegation to the fringe of society. Social exclusion is the process in which individuals are blocked from (or denied full access to) various rights, opportunities and resources that are normally available to members of a different group, and which are fundamental to social integration and observance of human rights within that particular group (e.g., housing, employment, healthcare, civic engagement, democratic participation, and due process). The outcome of social exclusion is that affected individuals or communities are prevented from participating fully in the economic, social, and political life of the society in which they live.

Social exclusion at the individual level results in an individual's exclusion from meaningful participation in society. Many communities experience social exclusion, such as racial (e.g., black), caste (e.g., untouchables in India), and economic communities.

Some characteristics of marginalized groups are summed up as follow:

- 1) They suffer from discrimination and subordination.
- 2) They have physical and/or cultural traits that set them apart, and which are disapproved of, by a dominant group.
- 3) They share a sense of collective identity and common burdens.
- 4) They have shared social rules about who belongs, and who does not

Specifically, BioGov.net project will focus on women, ethnic and religious minorities, migrants and refugees, the LGBTIQ community, disabled persons, youth and the elderly, acknowledged as marginalized groups by our project. It is proposed not to focus on a single marginalised group in BioGov.net but to work with different types of people including a) conformists b) dependent people, c) survivors and d) entrepreneurs.

3.4.2.2 How to engage marginalized, disadvantaged and minority groups

Keeping in mind the definition of marginalized, disadvantaged and minority groups in the previous chapter, one of the first steps for local CoPs, is to determine which groups are considered as marginalized in their own regional community and why this is the case. Racial discrimination may be salient in some regions, while poverty is the main concern in others and the potential intersection is self-evident. To avoid leaving behind those who need to be engaged most, local CoP leaders need to promote inclusion, listening, and diverse approaches to engagement. The first step in this process is developing an understanding of

² Cohesion policy and marginalized communities-Briefing, European Parliamentary Research Service, October 2016

³ <https://eige.europa.eu/thesaurus/terms/1280>

the community landscape and answering questions such as: Who is in local community? What challenges do these groups face? What is their relationship with previous cooperation contexts (with the local government, with local networks etc)? How can the leader overcome any lingering hurdles from previous interactions? What does the community has to offer to meet the specific needs of this group?⁴

When stepping into an engagement process, it is important to recognize that marginalized groups may very well have pre-existing relationships and prior experiences with local initiatives. Those prior experiences will influence and frame any future interactions with the community. The first step in the process of engaging such groups is to meet them and start listening to their experiences to best understand how can proceed to bridge divides. In the context of BioGov.net, this process can take the form of digital and in-person surveys, facilitated discussion workshops, conversations of local Community of Practice gatherings, and mutual learning events. In this stage, the designated CoP Leader is crucial; since that individual or team must have a keen, comprehensive understanding of the people they are about to involve, as well as an ability to connect with the community. Building relationships is part of the initial step of marginalized groups engagement before building connections with the entire community.

According to CITISPYCE (FP7 project) there is a specific methodology to work with these groups. The project has focused on policies targeting disadvantaged young people and, among other matters, has uncovered a range of initiatives undertaken by and for disadvantaged young people to help tackle their inequalities⁵.

The model assumes that neither marginalised groups in general nor members of any one category are homogeneous, therefore no intervention will work effectively with all individuals and in all situations. The inability of social policies to tackle inequalities is frequently due to the inadequacy of their approach when addressing disadvantaged young people, for example offering educational activities in a traditional sense (teacher talking to a class, coach talking to a client), which are not suitable for everyone. For certain groups, alternative forms of education, such as informal education, peer-to-peer learning, or innovative approaches using the arts will be more suitable.

The model (see Figure 2) proposes to seek a strong intervention logic based on the **specific characteristics** of an individual and to adopt **different strategies** to address different individuals (regardless of which marginalised group they belong to). It is, for example, necessary to see how they perceive their situation and how they view themselves (ambitions) and their competencies (abilities), which can then be used to identify the best strategy for their development.

Taking into account the fact that standard educational formats are not suitable for all groups, it was also recommended to broaden the definition of 'education' to 'development', which can result in the development of specific skills or competencies in non-formal or informal settings.

⁴ <https://icma.org/articles/pm-magazine/engaging-marginalized-communities-challenges-and-best-practices>

⁵ <http://www.citispisce.eu/>

Figure 2 Individual strategies addressing disadvantaged young people

Source: Effective Interventions for Unemployed Young People in Europe – Unemployed Young People in Europe- Social Innovation or Paradigm Shift? Edited by Tomáš Sirovátka and Henk Spies, 2017, ISBN9781315279138, DOI <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315279138>

3.4.3 Guiding principles for inclusion of all types of stakeholders

The CoP protocols introduce specific principles to ensure the effective inclusion of the diverse identified stakeholder groups in the different activities of BioGov.net. In particular, the principles to be followed by project partners are laid out below, with respect to the **inclusion** of stakeholders in the activities of BioGov.net as well as **regional representation** and **gender aspects**, also including marginalized groups and/or NEETs.

Table 6 Guiding principles for stakeholder inclusion in project activities

Category	Guiding principles
Inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure participation in project activities from the full range of potentially interested stakeholders spanning across the entire range of the key stakeholder groups identified. • Timely identify any potential barriers to the participation of the interested stakeholders in the activities of the project (such as accessibility, long geographic distances, lack of awareness). • Assess and determine effective means of surpassing potential barriers to participation (such as broad and targeted information sharing via online means and other suitable channels, etc.). • Appropriately take into account the needs, interests and potential conflicts that may arise among the targeted stakeholder groups in the framework of their participation in the project activities.

Category	Guiding principles
Regional representation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure a good representation of different regions within and among countries in regional CoP to the extent possible. • Address and engage with stakeholders within focal regions of the project but also from beyond, based on the access of partners to relevant networks and initiatives.
Gender aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide equal opportunities and access for all genders and age groups (involving also marginalized and/or NEETs) to project activities such as the development and validation of the BioGov.net recommendations, best practices guidelines and training governance • Maintain ethical communication standards by respecting the dignity of individuals as well as by eliminating any form of gender-related bias in communication campaigns of the project. • Engage in constructive discussions with stakeholders participating in project activities on the progress of BioGov.net in implementing its commitment to gender balance.

3.5 Rights and duties

The following table summarises the rights and duties of stakeholders participating in the regional CoP, as provided in the respective Terms of Reference (Annex II).

Table 7: Right and duties of CoPs members

Rights	Duties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders participate in the CoP voluntarily and have the right to withdraw at any time or refuse participation without facing any adverse consequences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders agree to abide by the Terms of Reference which explain in further detail expected involvement as well as terms pertaining to their membership.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders' have the right to preserve their anonymity during all project activities they will be involved in and in reports or publications produced 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders participate in their individual capacity and not delegate any expected work to another person without prior written agreement.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders have the right to request further processing and storage of their data by the consortium to be ceased without having to justify their request. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders ensure that they are involved in project activities in complete independence and there is no conflict of interest affecting their participation.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders have the right to access project results ahead of their public release in order to provide input for fine-tuning them in alignment with the needs of their users. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders must not disclose any information provided to them in the frame of BioGov.net activities and fully respect all confidentiality requirements.

3.6 Performance strategy

In this section, the management process and various roles in the frame of CoP are described, as well as the procedure for monitoring the operation of CoP and tracking progress in relation to project KPIs and targets for stakeholder engagement along with tools designed to facilitate the process.

3.6.1 Roles in the context of the CoPs

The BioGov.net CoPs are set-up and operated to share knowledge, expertise, and feedback with the consortium of the project in key implementation stages. The role of CoP in the context of the project may be summed up as follows:

- Provide relevant information to the BioGov.net consortium by participating (based on voluntary basis) in project co-creation events/workshops of the project, get involved in related discussions, share knowledge, exchange experience (peer to peer dialog) on good practices, the results of which will procure a basis for the fine-tuning, roll-out and replication of the BioGov.net training framework.
- Support the network for bio-based stakeholders in the transition towards bioeconomy uptake. Contribute at identifying key elements.
- Provide case studies by participating in discussions about training, and retraining availabilities in the region, by identifying the skills gaps and policies' limitation.

To fulfil this role, it is envisaged that local CoPs, during the project, will operate through physical and digital means in the project activities. The main outcome of CoPs is to offer feedback loop from the society to the policy makers using the inclusive methods as designathons (or alternatively focus groups and co-creation workshops), co-design events, policy workshops, and best practice guidelines for local operators and innovation developers giving them the opportunity to interact, if necessary, in multi stakeholders' consultation.

In each country/region a CoP has been established by a consortium partner who is responsible for setting-up and managing the local CoP. The role of each CoP Leader foresees the following:

- i. to identify, select and recruit members during the set-up phase of their CoP;
- ii. to undertake all communications with stakeholders and provide all necessary information to members about the project activities involving the CoP;
- iii. to organise and carry out the project activities in their country/region, including interviews, workshops and events among others (more specific information on activities involving CoP are provided in Chapter 4); and
- iv. to collect feedback and produce valuable outputs in the frame of these activities.

3.7 Performance monitoring and tracking of results

In order to keep track of the project activities in which members of the CoP participate, a dedicated methodological tool has been designed and will be employed, namely the Stakeholder Matrix (Annex VI). In particular, the Stakeholder Matrix captures the identified stakeholder groups of BioGov.net along with the expected role of each one for the relevant activities foreseen throughout the project, with a view to guiding project partners in the process of selecting the most suitable types to engage. It is also designed to keep track of stakeholder inclusion, regional representativeness and gender aspects. This will enable project partners to monitor the results of stakeholder engagement, as well as timely, assess and perform any needed corrective actions to better align them to the project's objectives.

With the above in mind, the Stakeholder Matrix follows a clear and simple structure:

- Stakeholder groups: The first column of the matrix lists the different stakeholder groups included in the CoP as identified in this report.

- **Demographics:** The following four columns aim at collecting anonymised data for quantifying the results of stakeholder engagement with respect to organization type, region/nation and gender.
- **Activities:** The rest of the columns are designed to collect information with respect to the participation of the stakeholder groups in the project activities.

Annex VI provides an illustrative overview of the template to be used by partners responsible for each CoP to elaborate, maintain and update their own version of the Stakeholder Matrix. In this framework, the monitoring process to be followed is outlined below:

- The internal Stakeholder Matrix will be kept within the context of CoP Leader who has received the Informed Consent form of CoP members participating in the local CoP.
- CoP Leaders will set up their own internal Stakeholder Matrix ensuring the confidentiality of the data included (GDPR). In this respect, the Stakeholder matrix will include data about key stakeholder groups and individual stakeholders. These will be classified by organisation name, contact person (incl. gender, region/nation) and contact details.
- The CoP Leaders will be asked to send an anonymised Stakeholder Matrix (only organization type, gender and region/country) to WP3 Leader (Wissenschaftsladen Bonn) for aggregating the data in to the D3.2. A trimester update of the anonymised Stakeholder Matrix for each local CoP may be asked by the WP3 Leader, to better monitor the evolution of work, the stakeholders' continuous engagement and the participation or respective stakeholders in different project activities.

By using the Stakeholder Matrix, the WP3 Leader will coordinate the delivery mechanism of CoPs under Task 3.2 and, in cooperation with the Dissemination and Communication Manager (Task 6.2), will monitor the participation rates in various activities and related KPIs, reporting them in future updates of the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan (M36 of the project).

4 Activities involving CoPs & methodologies for their engagement

This Chapter describes the different activities, events and workshops in which the stakeholders will be invited to participate. It also contains useful methodological tools for organizing the different events, including objectives, baseline agenda and expected outcomes for each type of event. The tools provided below can be modified to meet the respective event topic.

Stakeholders participating in local CoPs will be involved in discussions, share knowledge, and exchange experience (peer to peer dialogue) in the frame of BioGov.net. As stated before, their participation is on a voluntary basis. Members of CoPs will contribute to these actions by engaging in interviews, co-creation and co-design workshops, focus groups and project events. The following table summarizes the provisional set of project activities foreseen for members of all CoPs, as well as a tentative timeline for their organization.

Table 8: Activities involving CoP members

Activities	Timing
Identifying, developing and validating relevant and suitable best practices and highlight success stories (T2.1)	M1-M6
Conduct collection and assessment of the EU and regional data and local communities' specificities (T2.2)	M4-M10
Participate in regional designathons (alternatively focus groups and co-creation workshops) ⁶ (8 in total) to tackle the regional challenges (T3.2.1)	M10-M16
Participate in regional co-design workshops, in order to provide input and validate bioeconomy training and mentoring guidelines (T3.2.2)	M14-M18
Participate in 8 policy workshops, one in each respective CoP region, to address the gaps in current governance systems and feedback loops for better strategy design in bioeconomy skills	M28-M34
Offer inputs from each stakeholders' networks (T4.1)	M1-M12
Participate in 8 regional (onsite) focus groups with regional stakeholders and 1 European (online) workshop to derive transnational guidelines and methodologies for training (5.1)	M12-M18
Participate in european co-creation workshops: 2 mutual learning/co-creation workshops will be organised by the consortium partners in their respective countries/ regions (T5.2.1)	M15-M30
Communication of activities, dissemination of results between CoP members to maximize the impact of the project (T6.2)	M1- M36

As part of the Dissemination and Communication strategy, the Communication and Dissemination Manager has provided the CoP Leaders with agenda templates, poster templates and the project leaflet to be used throughout the CoP activities, starting from the

⁶ BioGov.net Grant Agreement is under amendment process by the time D3.1 is delivered. Each designathon may be alternatively substituted by a focus group and a co-creation workshop.

members recruitment to the workshops organisation. These templates will be used during both online and offline communication to engage with CoP members. The most suitable will be used depending on the purpose of interaction.

A series of national and regional participatory workshops to co-create, access and collect feedback on the progress of training guidelines development will be organized in each country. More specifically, WP3 - besides setting up the CoPs - focuses also on activating the regional CoPs by organising regional events. Each regional event, involving the CoP, will have a dedicated thematic focus deriving from other Work Packages. During the CoP events, the stakeholders will be asked to provide insights and guidance for WP2, WP4 and WP5 activities and will also validate the results of delivered tasks under the relevant Work Packages.

Table 9: Specific events involving CoPs and their purpose

Events	Timing	Activities	Purpose of the event
Focus group (WP2) -as alternative event to the designathon ⁷	April/May 2023	CoPs validate the concepts/topics identified during regional desk-research	Analysing knowledge gaps, barriers, and facilitators, identify actors and offers in the bio-based educational ecosystem
Co-creation workshop (WP4) -as alternative event to the designathon	Summer 2023	Training and skills development opportunities and needs for each region from CoP point of view, feeds into and validates WP4 activities	Identify good practices and highlight success stories (case studies) in biobased trainings and support the employment in bio-based sector
Co-design workshop (WP4)	Sept. 2023	Validate concepts/tools for D4.1	Establish consultation mechanisms for the preparation of guidelines
Co-evaluation (WP5)	Oct. 2023	Outcome is the description of the validation process for the training and mentoring guidelines, D5.1. The process can be used again to validate D4.2 later on	Regional point of view
Policy workshop	Spring 2024	Policy topics. Also, D4.2 validation by CoPs	Provide recommendations to national bioeconomy policy, regarding the governance model and in relation to education-related strategies

⁷ Since BioGov.net Grant Agreement is under amendment, the designathon will be split in a focus group and a co-creation workshop in each CoP region, after the official approval. To anticipate all needs, this deliverable offers methodology description for all events.

4.1 Designathon

A Designathon is an event where stakeholders come together to work collaboratively and solve a specific design challenge within a set timeframe, working on a broadly defined challenge for social good, as for example training in the field of bioeconomy. This approach has proven especially effective when there is no clear vision or just a rough idea for an entirely new solution.

The aim is to tackle the regional challenges regarding the feedstock, technology, social inclusion, the role of novel technologies, cultural and heritage aspects in bioeconomy, training and skills development opportunities by proposing training needs and job profiles need to propose training based on identified needs and suggest job profiles' needs to be met in training and mentoring guidelines design.

Designathons usually end with a hands-on product or solution.

4.1.1 Objectives of Designathon

Designathon is a collaborative and intensive event that brings together different Bioeconomy stakeholders to tackle complex problems and create innovative solutions. The objectives of Designathon are to:

- Foster Creativity and Innovation. Participants are encouraged to think outside the box and come up with unconventional solutions to complex problems.
- Solve Real-world Problems and challenges. Participants work on problems that are relevant to society and have the potential to create a positive impact.
- Promotes cross-functional Collaboration, bringing together designers, developers, and problem-solvers from diverse backgrounds and skill sets. This collaboration allows participants to learn from each other, share ideas, and create holistic solutions.
- Provides an intensive learning experience for participants. It challenges them to work under pressure, think critically, and solve complex problems in a short amount of time. Participants also have the opportunity to learn from experienced mentors and industry experts.
- Provides an opportunity for participants to network and build relationships with other professionals in their field. Participants can also gain exposure to potential employers and clients, as well as develop their professional skills.

Overall, the objectives of Designathon are to promote creativity, collaboration, learning, and innovation, while addressing real-world problems and creating solutions that have the potential to make a positive impact on society⁸.

Designathons can constitute a platform for promoting design thinking and innovation. By bringing together people with diverse backgrounds and skill sets. They can showcase the power of design to solve complex problems and create positive change.

4.1.2 Baseline agenda

A Designathon is an intensive event that typically lasts anywhere from 24 to 48 hours. During this time, participants work collaboratively to address a specific challenge or problem. Here is a baseline agenda for a Designathon:

Day 1:

⁸ <https://www.designathonworks.com/method>

- Morning: Participants arrive and register. The opening ceremony and keynote speech are held, setting the tone for the event and introducing the problem to be solved.
- Mid-morning: Team formation takes place, allowing participants to network and form cross-functional teams.
- Late-morning: Problem definition and brainstorming session, where teams identify the key problems and challenges, they will be tackling.
- Afternoon: Ideation and prototyping session, where teams start to develop and refine their bioeconomy ideas.
- Evening: Dinner and social activities, allowing participants to relax and network with each other.

Day 2:

- Morning: Prototyping and testing, where teams work on refining their prototypes and testing them with real users.
- Mid-morning: Mentorship sessions, where teams receive guidance and advice from experienced mentors and industry experts.
- Afternoon: Finalization of prototypes and presentation preparation, where teams work on refining their presentations and rehearsing their pitches.
- Late-afternoon: Presentation of final solutions to a panel of judges and audience.
- Evening: Closing ceremony and celebration, where winners are announced, and participants reflect on their experiences and accomplishments.

This baseline agenda allows for a structured and intensive event that promotes collaboration, ideation, and prototyping while also allowing for networking opportunities.

Alternatively to the designathon and to avoid the intensity of a two-day engagement of the stakeholders (and also keeping in mind the ongoing amendment of BioGov.net Grant Agreement), the CoP leader can split the designathon methodology into a focus group and a co-creation workshop.

4.2 Focus Group

A focus group follows a simple yet impactful methodology to implement. It is a qualitative research method that brings together a small group of people (8-10 persons) to answer questions in a moderated setting. The group meets to explore and discuss a predefined topic and answers questions designed to shed light on a topic of interest. The group shares its feedback, opinions, knowledge, and insights about the topic at hand. Participants openly share opinions and are free to convince other participants of their ideas over discussion. The mediator/organizer takes notes on the discussion and opinions of group members. The right group members affect the results of the research, so it's vital that participants are selected members on the field under study (e.g. bioeconomy, training and education)⁹

4.2.1 Baseline Agenda

A baseline agenda for the focus groups could be the following:

Welcome and overview: The host introduces himself/herself and explains the purpose and process of the focus group.

Introductions by all participants: Each participant is asked to introduce himself/herself (Name, Organisation, Position, Experience on Bioeconomy) and share one thing he/she is really fond

⁹ <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/focus-group/>

of Bioeconomy (this question helps everyone to start on a positive note by thinking about why they like getting involved in activities related to Bioeconomy sector)

Address 3-4 predetermined questions: The host/moderator asks the first question, then goes around the table and has each person speak. As he/she asks the next questions, he/she encourages participants to speak when they choose. The host ensures that each person has an opportunity to talk about each question. To motivate the group, the host may ask:

- Who else has thoughts about this – maybe something a little different?
- What else have people experienced in this area?
- You've been discussing several different ideas; what haven't we heard yet?
- We want to hear all your opinions. Who has something else to discuss?

Summarize the discussion: The host/moderator briefs in two-to-three-minute summary the main themes heard and asks participants: "did I correctly described what was said?"

Thanks, and closing: The host warmly thanks everyone for participating. Explains how he/she plans to use the information and what is planned as future activity and how participants will be engaged.

4.3 Co-creation workshops

The methodology of **co-creation** emerges from transformative processes in the entrepreneurial world and aims at generating new products and services. For example, big companies and brands carry out effective collaborative creation actions involving users to develop new products and services but also to face structural changes as well as helping to solve new challenges in the internal management. This approach has been taken up by other fields, such as education, arts or the publishing sector¹⁰. In the context of BioGov.net , the co-creation workshops following the focus groups in each Region, are expected to capture the initial thoughts and needs of the local stakeholders.

4.3.1 Baseline Agenda

A baseline agenda for a co-creation workshop could be the following:

- Welcome and introduction
- Project overview, objectives and outputs
- Scope of the workshop and results from previous WPs (work done, good practices identified etc) on bioeconomy education and skills
- Brief presentation of the results of surveys and feedback from participants
- Discussion through interactive platform or sticky notes on boards
- Conclusions and final remarks¹¹

¹⁰ https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/D3-3_Guidebook-on-engagement-and-co-creation-methods_final.pdf

¹¹Based on transition 2bio Co-creation Workshop Agenda https://eubionet.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Agenda_Future-skills-for-Bioeconomy_Forestry.pdf

4.3.2 Methodologies & Tools for co-creation

The following indicative methodologies can be used from the CoP leader during a designathon or during co-creation workshops. The methodologies encourage interaction, and exchange in a collaborative and creative way, bringing together people from different backgrounds to intentionally connect multiple ideas and perspectives on a topic by engaging participants in several rounds of conversation.

World Café Method

Drawing on seven integrated design principles, the World Café methodology¹² is a simple, effective, and flexible format for hosting large group dialogue. Each element of the method has a specific purpose and corresponds to one or more of the design principles.

Duration: 90 minutes to 2.5 hours

Use

- explore a topic from multiple perspectives
- encourage participants to make new connections

Needs

World Café can be modified to meet a wide variety of needs. Specifics of context, numbers, purpose, location, and other circumstances are factored into each event's unique invitation, design, and question choice, but the following five components comprise the basic model:

1) Setting: Create a "special" environment, most often modeled after a café, i.e. small round tables covered with a checkered or white linen tablecloth, butcher block paper, colored pens, a vase of flowers, and optional "talking stick" item. There should be four chairs at each table (optimally) – and no more than five.

2) Welcome and Introduction: The host begins with a warm welcome and an introduction to the World Café process, setting the context, sharing the Café Etiquette, and putting participants at ease.

3) Small-Group Rounds: The process begins with the first of three or more twenty-minute rounds of conversation for small groups of four (five maximum) people seated around a table. At the end of the twenty minutes, each member of the group moves to a different new table. They may or may not choose to leave one person as the "table host" for the next round, who welcomes the next group and briefly fills them in on what happened in the previous round.

4) Questions: each round is prefaced with a question specially crafted for the specific context and desired purpose of the World Café. The same questions can be used for more than one round, or they may build upon each other to focus the conversation or guide its direction.

5) Harvest: After the small groups (and/or in between rounds, as needed), individuals are invited to share insights or other results from their conversations with the rest of the large group. These results are reflected visually in a variety of ways, most often using graphic recording in the front of the room.

Scenario forecast method

Duration: 60 minutes

Use

¹² See <https://theworldcafe.com/key-concepts-resources/world-cafe-method/>

- Elicit expectations
- Exploring possibilities
- Detecting opportunities

Needs

- Big board/wall with an axis cross
- Post-its:

Yellow: Bio economy stakeholders

Blue: actions

Green: content

Orange: objectives

- Small red and green circular stickers
- Examples of one or two previous elaborated scenarios in order to inspire

Instructions

1. Imagine what would be the opportunities in the selected sector/theme/area in the near future related to an application that uses (open) cultural bioeconomy content. Try to focus on the tool (or feature of a tool) that will allow that, rather than abstract situations.

2. Work in groups of 3/4 people and think of possible scenarios. Write it down in one sentence using 4 post-its of different colours, starting with the words “[What if as a <role>], [I could <desired action>] [<with this content>] [so <benefit>]” Use at least one verb, describing an action, and a type of content.

3. Follow this structure and the examples:

Yellow: Bio economy stakeholders

Blue: actions

Green: content

Orange: objectives

4. Put the sentence on the wall and present it to the stakeholders group. The rest of participants (depending on their role) are invited to add possibilities and alternatives, or to narrow down the scenario according to the colour of post-its they have (actions, content, goals).

5. After sharing and working on scenarios from all participants, give a title to your scenario (considering the initial sentence, as well as the other possibilities around it).

6. Place the title of your scenario on the whiteboard, considering its level of technological complexity, as well as its potential in the area/theme/sector of the session.

7. Other participants can ask you to move it around the axis according to their opinion, only if they explain briefly why.

8. Once all the scenarios are on the axis, use markers (circular stickers) to indicate the most interesting options/features from your point of view. (Red light: not interesting // Green light: I will go for it) Discuss if needed.

9. Select from there which scenarios fit better for co-designing a pilot or adding features to it, in order to narrow things down and keep on working around it in groups.

4.3.3 Outputs

The outcome of a co-creation activity can vary depending on the nature of the challenge and the goals of the event. Typically, co-creation activities aim to produce ideas and innovative

solutions to real-world problems. The outcomes of a co-creation can include prototypes, designs, and ideas that have the potential to make a positive impact on society.

Co-creation workshops may produce valuable outputs from ideation and brainstorming over the topic under discussion and address solutions for specific needs identified.

The outcomes can be of different nature dependant the chosen aims and creative techniques. They can include videos, art, written texts as well as practical solutions or innovative ideas. It is possible to co-create different types of outputs and combining various outputs which may give different participants opportunities to share their knowledge and acquire new skills. Co-creation workshops will produce both creative and research outputs. Different participants can influence each other and learn from each other. That is why, co-creation activities are considered a valuable means to foster collaboration and networking among participants, which can lead to new professional opportunities and partnerships. Participants stakeholders can learn from each other's skills, experiences, and perspectives, which can enhance their own practices and broaden their horizons.

In summary, the outcomes of co-creation workshops can include ideas, practical and innovative solutions to real-world problems, collaboration and networking opportunities, and the promotion of innovation.

4.4 Co-Design Workshops

Co-design workshops are a space for “creative collaboration”. It is rooted in participatory procedures and user-centred design and aims to involve stakeholders in the early phases of the design process often referred to as “fuzzy front end”. The level of involvement can vary from informing the project to having the role ‘user-as-a-partner’ in designing, based on the idea that everyone can be creative. The emphasis is more on designing with the people rather than designing for the people. It is a tool for discovery and exploring opportunities rather than producing final solutions, and aims to start discussion among CoPs stakeholders, guide design decisions, for example by building concepts, which inform what should be designed and for whom.¹³

The aim of regional co-design workshops in BioGov.net project is to define the key drivers for national bioeconomy and provide the input and validation to bioeconomy training and mentoring guidelines. In total 2¹⁴ co-design workshops will be organized in each region in collaboration with local museums, science/art centres, facilitating social innovation, implementing new social practices, and enabling social ownership for inputs to strategic choices for bioeconomy wider uptake. Co-design workshops will produce suggestions to local needs under reflection of the CoPs.

4.4.1 Objectives of co-design workshops

Co-design workshops are collaborative sessions where stakeholders work together to design and develop solutions to complex problems. For this, used fast-paced activities to generate ideas and construct rough concepts through prototypes. The objectives of co-design workshops are multi-faceted, and they go beyond merely designing a solution. Some of the primary objectives of co-design workshops are:

¹³ <https://medium.com/@gyngyifekete/designing-a-co-design-workshop-7686eaf4bf0f>

¹⁴ Initially, the co-design workshops for each CoP are 3, but the GA under amendment will foresee 2 co-design workshops.

- To promote collaboration and co-creation among stakeholders. The goal is to create a shared understanding of the problem and to work together to develop a solution that meets the needs of all stakeholders.
- An opportunity for stakeholders to voice their opinions and contribute to the design process. The workshop encourages active participation and empowers stakeholders to take ownership of the solution.
- To drive better design outcomes as they bring together diverse perspectives, ideas, and skills. The workshop allows for the exploration of different design options and encourages stakeholders to challenge assumptions and provide constructive feedback.
- Can help to reduce the risk of failure by early identifying potential problems in the design process. The workshop allows for the testing of different design options and provides stakeholders with a better understanding of the potential outcomes of the solution.

Overall, the objectives of co-design workshops are to promote collaboration, empower stakeholders, improve design quality, increase buy-in, and reduce risk. By achieving these objectives, co-design workshops can lead to better design outcomes and ultimately, more effective solutions to complex problems.

4.4.2 Baseline agenda

A baseline agenda for the Co-design workshops could be the following:

Introduction: Introduce the workshop and its goals and explain the concept of bioeconomy.

Keynote speakers: Invite various stakeholders' and experts from the bioeconomy sector (research and higher education, industry, active communities etc) to share their insights and experience in the field of bioeconomy.

Group discussions: Break participants into groups and assign them a specific topic related to bioeconomy, such as sustainable agriculture, biotechnology, or circular economy. Participants should be encouraged to share their ideas and perspectives, and to brainstorm potential solutions.

Idea pitching: Each group presents their ideas to the whole workshop and receives feedback from other participants.

Refinement and prioritization: Groups should refine their ideas based on feedback and prioritize the most promising solutions.

Roadmap creation: Based on the prioritized solutions, participants should create a roadmap for implementation that outlines the necessary steps and resources required to achieve the proposed solutions.

Conclusion: Summarize the main ideas and outcomes of the workshop and thank participants for their contributions.

By following this agenda, co-design workshops based on bioeconomy can help foster collaboration and innovation towards a more sustainable future.

4.4.3 Methodologies – Tools

All the methodologies described in the following tools are indicative and partners may choose as they wish. When organizing co-design workshops, there are several tools available to facilitate collaboration and creativity among participants. These tools can be combined and

customized based on the specific needs and goals of the co-design workshop, ensuring a productive and collaborative environment for all participants.

“Appetizer” Method (Show me your app)¹⁵

Duration: 30-60 minutes

Use

- “Ice-breaker” previous to other activities, at the beginning of the workshop
- Inspiration for development
- Initial agreement on indicators for evaluation

Needs

- Quiet space with good wi-fi (in case of digital participations) and tables or chairs for small groups
- Smart phones, laptops, or tablets from participants
- Voting board, with indicator of levels such as:
 - Innovation (+/-)
 - Feasibility (+/-)
 - Engagement (+/-)
 - “Potential” in that specific theme or area (+/-)
 - Adaptability (+/-)

Instructions

1. In groups of 2 or 3 people, show each other your inspirational case study on Bioeconomy for interaction. Explain each other why. It doesn't have to be focused on a specific theme but something you like to play with or use, ideally in that context, or you think is original. You have 10 minutes each to show your favourite case study to the rest of the group and promote it.
2. Now decide which one is better as an inspiration for BioGov.net project diffusion. Questions to ask: “How will this good case study used in a concrete environment (education, business, design, etc)?” “How could it be useful to promote bioeconomy?”
3. Present the selected case study to the rest of the group, with your insights. Place the screen device on the table so all participants see the app, and a number next to it.
4. Equalize! What's the best-case study we could be inspired by, as a whole or according to some of its main features? Move the tokens according to the indicators on the board.
5. Voting! After checking all the levels of each project, lets decide which case study wins, discussing why based on its main features.
6. The case study with highest scores wins (ideally, the host may invite the members for a coffee to celebrate the results)¹⁶

¹⁵https://pro.europeana.eu/files/Europeana_Professional/Projects/Project_list/Europeana_Creative/WP1%20-%20Europeana%20Open%20Laboratory/Methodologies%20for%20Co-Creation%20Workshops%20with%20Europeana%20Content.pdf

¹⁶https://pro.europeana.eu/files/Europeana_Professional/Projects/Project_list/Europeana_Creative/WP1%20-%20Europeana%20Open%20Laboratory/Methodologies%20for%20Co-Creation%20Workshops%20with%20Europeana%20Content.pdf

Content workshop Method (alternative “ice-breaker”)

Duration: 30-60 minutes

Use

- Ice-breaker previous to other activities
- Inspiration for development
- Inspiration for content/metadata requirements

Needs

- Exhibition space or public space with enough heritage content or museum /art centre or public space
- Smart phones or tablets from participants (also available equipment for remote participation)
- post-its of different colours
- Large rectangular table
- Main tablet/screen for showing pictures from participants
- (Ideally) portable printer (if there's not enough screen devices)

Instructions

1. Form small teams of 2/3 people related to Bioeconomy (for example Bio art exhibitions). You're a “collection scout” (look for offline contents that have something in common).
2. Each group gets at least 4 pictures from what they see around (objects, walls, displays, people, interactions). It can be any idea of a set you consider important in what you see for the area/theme selected.
3. Select in groups the best findings you have for art and bioeconomy / bio-based solutions, choosing the most interesting 3 items you decide.
4. Send the selected files to a drive folder and/or share it in the same device as a sideshow.
5. Each team shows and explains the collection they have arranged to the rest of participants (pencil of natural organic wood with seeds in the end, notebook made of elephant dung and recycled paper, and coloured with natural dyes, etc.).
6. Put the device (tablet, mobile, laptop) containing the sideshow of your collection on the table.
7. Tag any collection, using one word per post-it (depending on the colour), in order to classify it according to:
 - a. Bioeconomy skills needed to design and produce art bioproducts (yellow post-its)
 - b. Gaps between training and solutions (blue post-its)
 - c. Biobased solutions to promote Bioeconomy (orange post-its)
8. Identify the tags which repeat in each collection, then discuss: Are the suggested skills necessary and helpful for Biobased production? Which is the best way to promote Biobased solutions? Which of these tags could be useful or interesting for creative uses?
9. Identify unique tags (if they are) in any of the collections, or the most significant/unexpected/useful ones for you, then discuss: Can it be used to motivate/inspire different types of artists, using biological materials to educate in Bioeconomy?

4.4.4 Outputs

Co-design workshops are a collaborative process that brings together stakeholders, designers, and end-users to co-create solutions for complex problems. The outputs of co-design workshops can vary depending on the goals of the workshop and the needs of the participants. Some possible outputs could be:

- A wealth of new ideas and concepts that address the problem at hand. These ideas can be developed through brainstorming, ideation exercises, and collaborative discussions.
- Production of physical or digital prototypes and models that help stakeholders visualize and test potential solutions. These prototypes can be made using a variety of materials and can range from low-fidelity sketches to high-fidelity interactive models.
- Better understanding of their end-users by creating user personas and journey maps. These tools can help designers empathize with their end-users, identify pain points, and design solutions that meet their needs.
- Production of design principles and guidelines that help guide the design process. These principles can be used to ensure that designs are consistent, user-centered, and meet the needs of all stakeholders.
- Delivery of action plans that outline the steps needed to implement the solutions generated during the workshop. These plans can include timelines, resource requirements, and responsibilities for each stakeholder involved in the implementation process.

4.5 Policy workshops

Policy workshops are structured meetings that are organized gatherings where policymakers, experts, stakeholders, and other interested parties come together to discuss, analyze, and develop policies related to a specific issue or topic (In our case about Bioeconomy). The workshop aims to identify the key policy issues, generate new ideas and solutions, develop consensus among participants, and inform policy development and implementation. Policy workshops are often organized by government agencies and other organizations involved in policy development. They typically involve a series of presentations, discussions, and interactive activities that allow participants to share their perspectives, knowledge, and experiences. The outcomes of policy workshops can include reports, policy briefs, and other materials that summarize the discussions and recommendations made during the workshop. These outcomes can be used to inform policy development, advocacy efforts, and other related activities.

Policy workshops can be an important mechanism for engaging stakeholders and experts in the policy development process and promoting informed and evidence-based decision-making.

4.5.1 Objectives of policy workshops

The primary objectives of policy workshops include:

- Identify and define key policy issues related to a specific topic. The workshop brings together experts and stakeholders to discuss and analyze the issue, which helps in developing a clear understanding of the problem and its implications.
- Policy workshops provide a platform for participants to brainstorm and generate new ideas and solutions to address the identified policy issues. These ideas and solutions can be used to inform policy development and implementation.
- Develop consensus among stakeholders and experts on the policy issues and solutions. The workshop provides a forum for participants to discuss and debate the issues, which helps in building a shared understanding and agreement.
- Engage Stakeholders: Policy workshops provide an opportunity to engage stakeholders in the policy development process. The workshop allows stakeholders to provide their input, feedback, and ideas, which can help in developing policies that are more relevant and effective.

In summary, the objectives of policy workshops include identifying and defining policy issues, generating ideas and solutions, developing consensus, informing policy development, and engaging stakeholders.

4.5.2 Baseline agenda

A policy workshop is a gathering of policymakers, experts, stakeholders, and interested parties to discuss and develop policy proposals. The purpose of a policy workshop is to bring together diverse perspectives and knowledge to develop a shared understanding of a problem and potential solutions.

A baseline agenda for a policy workshop could include the following:

Introduction and Overview: The workshop begins with an introduction by the organizer or moderator, providing an overview of the objectives, format, and expectations for the workshop.

Problem Identification: The workshop participants are then given an opportunity to identify and define the problem or issue at hand. This could involve a presentation, or a discussion led by a subject matter expert.

Bioeconomy Stakeholder Analysis: Participants then engage in a stakeholder analysis to identify who is affected by the problem and who should be involved in developing policy solutions.

Brainstorming: The group then engages in a brainstorming session to generate ideas for policy solutions.

Feasibility Assessment: Participants assess the feasibility of the proposed policy solutions, taking into account the political, social, economic, and legal contexts.

Prioritization: Participants prioritize the proposed policy solutions based on their potential impact, feasibility, and other relevant criteria.

Action Planning: The workshop concludes with an action planning session, where participants develop a plan for implementing the policy solutions.

By following this baseline agenda, a policy workshop can provide a structured and collaborative approach to policy development that leverages the expertise and knowledge of diverse stakeholders¹⁷.

4.5.3 Methodologies - Tools

The Case Method

Cases are narratives, situations, select data samplings, or statements that present unresolved and provocative issues, situations, or questions. The case method is a participatory, discussion-based way of learning where participants gain skills in critical thinking, communication, and group dynamics. It is a type of problem-based learning¹⁸. Often seen in the professional schools of medicine, law, and business, the case method is now used successfully in disciplines such as engineering, chemistry, education, and journalism. Participants can work through a case during class as a whole or in small groups.

In addition to the definition above, the case method of teaching (or learning):

- Is a partnership between various stakeholders' groups from the bioeconomy sector
- Promotes more effective contextual learning and long-term retention.
- Involves trust that stakeholders will find the answers.
- Answers questions not only of "how" but "why."
- Provides the opportunity to "walk around the problem" and to see varied perspectives¹⁹

The "case method" employs active learning, involves self-discovery where the participants serves as facilitator. It also builds the capacity for critical thinking: It uses questioning skills as modeled by the partners groups and employs discussion and debates and exercises an administrative point of view: Stakeholders must develop a framework for making decisions.

¹⁷ <https://thecompassforsbc.org/how-to-guide/how-conduct-stakeholder-workshop>

¹⁸ <https://citl.illinois.edu/unpublished/teaching-resources/teaching-strategies/problem-based-learning>

¹⁹ (Bruner, 2002, and Christensen, Garvin, and Sweet, 1991)

It also offers an exchange and flow of ideas from one person to another and achieves trust, respect, and risk-taking and models the process of inductive learning-from-experience: It is valuable in promoting life-long learning. It also promotes more effective contextual learning and long-term retention.

Some ways to use the case method appropriately are:

1. Choose an appropriate case

Cases can be any of the following:

- Finished cases based on facts; these are useful for purposes of analysis.
- Unfinished open-ended cases; where the results are not clear yet, so the participants must predict, make suggestions, and conclusions.
- Fictional cases; the difficulty is in writing these cases so they reflect a real-world situation.
- Original documents, such as the use of news articles, reports, data sets, ethnographies; an interesting case would be to provide two sides of a scenario²⁰.

2. Develop effective questions

Think about ways to start the discussion such as using a hypothetical example or employing the background knowledge of the stakeholders.

3. Get participants groups prepared

To prepare for the next workshop ask stakeholders to think about the following questions:

- What is the problem or decision about Bioeconomy?
- Who is the key decision-maker?
- Who are the other people involved?
- What caused the problem?
- What are some underlying assumptions or objectives?
- What decision needs to be made?
- Are there alternative responses?

4. Set ground rules with the groups

For effective class discussion suggest the following:

- Carefully listen to the discussion, but do not wait too long to participate.
- Collaboration and respect should always be present.
- Provide value-added comments, suggestions, or questions. Strive to think of the class objective by keeping the discussion going toward constructive inquiry and solutions.

Other suggestions

- Make sure the participants have finished presenting their perspective before interjecting. Wait and check their body language before adding or changing the discussion.
- Take notes of the progress and the content in the discussion. One way is by using the board or computer to structure the comments. Another way, particularly useful where there is a conflict or multiple alternatives, is the two-column method. In this method, the speaker makes two columns: “For and Against” or “Alternative A and Alternative B.” All arguments/comments are listed in the respective column before discussions or evaluations occur. Don't forget to note supportive evidence.
- In addition to the discussion method, you can also try debates, role-plays, and simulations as ways to uncover the lesson from the case.
- If you decide to grade participation, make sure that your grading system is an accurate and defensible portrayal of the contributions.

²⁰ Indiana University Teaching Handbook, 2005

4.5.4 Outputs

The outputs of a policy workshop are critical for translating the ideas and discussions generated during the workshop into actionable policy proposals. Some common outputs of a policy workshop:

- The most important output of a policy workshop is a set of policy recommendations that are developed based on the ideas generated during the workshop. These recommendations should be actionable, evidence-based, and feasible.
- An action plan is a practical roadmap for implementing the policy recommendations and should outline the necessary steps, timelines, responsible parties, and resources needed to implement the policy proposals.
- Policy briefs are concise documents that summarize the policy recommendations, providing background information, evidence, and arguments for why the recommendations are necessary and feasible. These briefs are often distributed to policymakers, stakeholders, and the public to raise awareness and build support for the proposed policies.
- A summary report is a comprehensive document that captures the key insights, findings, and recommendations from the policy workshop, that can be used to inform future policymaking, research, and advocacy efforts.
- Network and Partnership Building: Policy workshops provide an opportunity for stakeholders and experts to build relationships, identify areas of mutual interest, and explore potential partnerships that can support the implementation of the policy recommendations.

The outputs of a policy workshop should be actionable, evidence-based, and communicated in a way that engages policymakers, stakeholders, and the public. These outputs are critical for turning the ideas generated during the workshop into tangible policy solutions that can make a positive impact on society²¹.

4.6 Mutual Learning (ML) Events

Mutual Learning (ML) events is a means of ensuring the engagement of all relevant groups and aim to tackle research and innovation related challenges by creating partnerships with a variety of perspectives, knowledge, and experience. These events will be organised under WP5 but are also referred to, in this Deliverable because they also involve the CoPs.

MLs bringing together a wide diversity of actors to deliberate and share on matters of science, technology, and innovation, they can ensure an evidence-based, both knowledge and value-driven approach in support of EU policies.

4.6.1 How to set up a ML

Setting up the infrastructure and logistics for the ML event is a key part of the overall event design, especially in terms of resources used and has an overarching effect on the quality of

²¹ <https://www.csap.cam.ac.uk/Research-Policy-Engagement/policy-workshops>

the event – starting from first contact with invitees until the generation of impactful outcomes. The set-up comprises of nine key steps:

- Draft a quality programme. The development of a programme for a ML event is the first step and is essential to engaging the right quadruple helix stakeholders for the event. The programme should contain at least:
 - a small paragraph regarding the objectives of the project,
 - a small paragraph outlining the issue/challenges to be addressed in the event
 - an outline of the objectives of the ML event
 - the key guiding questions
 - an agenda, including information on the venue and the catering if applicable.
- Develop invitations and communicate with invitees
- Select at least two appropriate facilitators that has sound understanding of the issues to be discussed as well as experience in facilitation and is familiar with the formats and methods selected.
- Find an attractive and functional venue
- Set-up chair order to engage
- Ensure facilitation and engagement tools are in place and work
- Regarding all outreach material and encouragements
- Select delicious and sustainable catering
- Check that all key aspects of organizing an ML event are covered

4.7 Feedback – how to get it

Bioeconomy workshops (focus groups, co-creation workshops, co-design workshops) are a great way to gather stakeholders from different sectors to discuss and share their ideas about how to create a sustainable economy based on the principles of biotechnology, ecology, and circularity. During these workshops, participants often identify feedback loops that can help to strengthen the bioeconomy and create more sustainable systems. Here are some of the feedback loops that have been identified in bioeconomy CoPs workshops:

1. The circularity feedback which means that waste products are transformed into valuable resources. In this feedback loop, waste products from one sector can be used as inputs for another sector, creating a closed loop system that reduces waste and increases efficiency.
2. Innovation feedback that can lead to new opportunities, which in turn can lead to further innovation. This loop helps to drive progress in the bioeconomy and keep it moving forward.
3. The stakeholder feedback loop to each other about their needs and requirements, helping to create a more balanced and equitable bioeconomy. They can also use feedback from one workshop to other so to create a connection between CoP events.
4. The policy feedback, that can impact the development of the bioeconomy, which can in turn influence future policy decisions. This loop helps to ensure that policies are well-informed and responsive to the needs of the bioeconomy.
5. The ecosystem feedback loop based on the principles of ecology, which means that it must be integrated into the natural environment. According to that, the health of the ecosystem impacts the bioeconomy, and the bioeconomy can in turn impact the health of the ecosystem. This loop helps to ensure that the bioeconomy is sustainable and resilient over the long term.

6. Feedback loops are critical for the success of the bioeconomy, as they help to create a dynamic and adaptable system that can respond to the needs of stakeholders, policy makers, and the natural environment²².

To collect feedback, a strategy should be followed: not all types of survey are the same or serve the same purpose. Surveys about each activity can take place during or after the event. The choice of timing will influence the type of feedback to be collected. Feedback surveys conducted during the event should be very short to avoid interrupting the participant's experience — although, when used well, they can be another element of the experience. They are useful for quickly and quantitatively measuring a specific aspect of the event, such as the presentations or even the attention paid to the audience at a particular time. For this purpose, surveys that are rating-based or that require no more than one click are very useful. You need a fairly large number of participants to respond in order to draw conclusions.

When the organizer wants to collect feedback on the event in general and gather more detailed comments from participants, it is advisable to conduct the survey after the event. However, do not give the participants too much time otherwise they will forget the experience! These surveys can be longer, with open questions and comments. They take more time so participation rate is often lower, but each answer has great value.

To encourage participation in surveys, you can reward respondents with a gift (for example a bioplastic water flask, or a small, recycled notebook) or a teaser (get free participation to another event).

Surveys to gather feedback from participants can take various forms, with responses being public or private, in the shape of a form or a note. Find the solution that best meets your needs and allows you to process the data appropriately.

Usually you will provide a link to receive feedback. With an e-mailing tool, the organizer can manage the sending of surveys to all participants quickly and easily. It is good practice to send a thank-you email in which you also include the link to the satisfaction survey.

Basic steps for a successful feedback loop are the following:

1. Collect data preferably by digital tools
2. Find a survey solution (e-mail survey, satisfaction survey,
3. Set the goals beforehand
4. Create different surveys for different audience segments.
5. design the feedback questionnaire

To deliver a successful feedback loop methodology and designing a feedback questionnaire, some tips should be remembered²³:

- Make the survey/questionnaire clear and simple to complete.
- Keep the survey as short as possible to achieve your objectives.
- Keep the questions as concise and clear as possible.
- Avoid non-essential questions.
- Alternate between closed and open questions.
- Ask questions about things you can do something about.

²² https://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_D4.2_Lessons_learned_from_BioSTEP.pdf

²³ <https://weezevent.com/en-gb/blog/collect-event-participants-feedback/>

5 Conclusions and way forward

The present report has outlined a protocol for establishing the BioGov.net actors structures, namely the Community of Practice (CoP) in eight focal countries and regions of the project across Europe with a pan-European focus and engaging their members to provide the consortium with feedback and information to produce demand-driven results.

More specifically, in the frame of the CoP protocol, the definition, the mission and expected structure of CoP have been defined along with a selection process based on selection criteria to be followed by partners during the set-up phase of these structures. Moreover, guidelines and supporting documents have been elaborated for contacting and engaging stakeholders in project activities as well as principles for ensuring their effective inclusion. Additionally, the rights and duties of members, guidelines for CoP management along with a list of activities in which the CoP members will be involved have been defined to ensure the smooth operation of CoP throughout the project. Methodologies and specific tools to organise events involving CoPs and receive feedback have been presented in this report to ease partners work and to set the common ground of activities evolution.

By using this guide, BioGov.net partners are expected to start engaging the stakeholders in their regional CoP.

Annexes

Annex I – Official Invitation Letter addressed to potential CoP Member

Subject: Invitation to join the Local Community of Practice in the context of the EU-funded project BioGov.net

Dear Stakeholder,

Partner Name as CoP Leader would like to invite you to join the BioGov.net Community of Practice (CoP) that is set up in **your country** under the framework of the EU-funded [BioGov.net](#) project.

BioGov.net aims strategically to support the establishment of innovative governance models in bioeconomy to achieve better-informed decision-making processes, social engagement of all actors and uptake of sustainable innovations in bioeconomy.

The Project will set up 8 local Communities of Practice, in 8 different countries/regions (Estonia, Greece, Portugal, Slovakia, Italy, Czechia, The Netherlands, Germany) that bring together various local stakeholders: research and higher education organisations, vocational organisations, citizens, NGOs & marginalised groups etc. BioGov.net applies a multi-stakeholder approach by bringing together the different stakeholder groups, by strengthening already existing educational networks (actors involved in adult learning, retraining and skills' development) and initiatives with pioneers in the field. Therefore, the inclusion of bio-systems (industries, SMEs, researchers), active communities (national cultural and natural heritage keepers, artists, designers, professionals' associations) but also citizen's organisations, policy makers and researcher's communities is one of the core activities of the project.

Partner Name is currently inviting select key actors actively involved in the bioeconomy sector to form the **<country/region name>** Community of Practice, to be actively involved in the project. You have been identified and selected as an important member of the bioeconomy stakeholder system within **<country/region name>** and we would be delighted to have you on board! In order to get a better overview of the project and your expected involvement as member of the Community of Practice, you can find further information in the attached Terms of Reference.

Please let us know if you are interested in becoming a member of the BioGov.net Community of Practice in **<country/region name>** Community of Practice by replying to this email by **xx.xx.xx23** and by sending us back a signed and scanned Declaration of Acceptance- using the attached template.

Should you have any further questions about the project or the Community of Practice, please do not hesitate to contact us.

We are looking forward to hearing from you!

Yours Sincerely,

Full Name

CoP Leader

Annex II – Terms of Reference for the CoP

Introduction

You have been invited to the **BioGov.net Community of Practice (CoP)** in **<country/region name>**. Community of Practice. The current document outlines the Terms of Reference that will help you understand what this involves before you decide to participate. Please take the time to carefully read this document and ask for any clarifications you may require. Questions may be sent to **Mr/Mrs XXXXXX**, responsible person and leader of the **<country/region name>** CoP.

Community of Practice (CoP) is a regional network of stakeholders coming from across the entire value chain of the bioeconomy sector as well as researchers, policy makers groups representing civil society, actors involved in adult learning, retraining and skills' development, inclusion of bio-systems (industries, SMEs), reaching a balanced participation.

The added value of BioGov.net in comparison to other successful projects on bioeconomy and training, is that it combines bioeconomy with art and wishes to address to active communities (national cultural and natural heritage keepers, artists, designers, professionals' associations), cultural and creative sectors but also marginalised groups. The art offers a new way to present bio-based products and applications to the public, in an easy conceivable way.

Partner Name will engage various stakeholders in various workshops (to be organized by the consortium partners in their respective countries/ regions from April 2023 (M11) to November 2024 (M30), in order to record their feedback and knowledge as well as their suggestions for training and mentoring needs. The CoP Members will actively participate in the project, identifying needs in bioeconomy education, skill gaps, and possibilities to use art and culture as a vehicle for successful inclusion of marginalized groups in bioeconomy and as a means to raise awareness and engage people in bioeconomy.

BioGov.net in a nutshell

BioGov.net is a three-year project (June 2022 to May 2025) funded by the Horizon Europe programme, composed by 10 experienced partners that will operationalise the project's activities in 8 EU countries: Estonia, Italy, The Netherland, Greece, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Portugal and Germany.

The bioeconomy is expected to be a motor for sustainability and a solution to a number of ecological and social challenges, including climate change, mitigation, cleaner production processes, economic growth, and new employment opportunities. However, despite all the efforts, the transition towards a sustainable bioeconomy is progressing too slow, and there is a need for establishing the means for exploring new paths to govern the transition process.

BioGov.net will contribute to establishing innovative governance models in the bioeconomy, providing an inclusive training and mentoring framework in specific European regions, aiming to build a bridge between knowledge and skills in the bioeconomy, secured by an effective governance.

Among the main activities of BioGov.net project, we highlight:

- Identify existing actions of good governance approaches on training and skills-building in the Bioeconomy in our 8 regions.
- Assess the regions' specificities, such as economic/cultural characteristics, regulatory/political barriers, educational/training availabilities, skills and jobs in demand in the bioeconomy, in order to develop governance and training resources tailored to the regions.

- Bring together more than 240 key actors from research and higher education organizations, vocational education organizations, industry, businesses (SMEs), policy makers and administrations, NGOs-marginalised group, active communities, cultural and creative sectors(C.C.Is) and citizens and wider society into 8 regional Communities of Practice that will operate in their region.
- Deliver modern training and mentoring guidelines to support permanent learning and re-training in areas related to the bioeconomy.

You can find out more information about BioGov.net and the consortium by visiting www.biogov.net.

Are you a bioeconomy researcher or academic?
A policy maker on bioeconomy or a bio-system industry?
Are you an Artist?
Or maybe a Fashion Designer on biodegradable products?
An active community member or a CCI?
Do you work with marginalised groups or with active citizens organisation?
Do you want to be part of our CoP?

Here are your benefits!

BioGov.net

Role and benefits

Role

The BioGov.net CoP are set-up and operated to share knowledge, expertise, and feedback with the consortium of the project in key implementation stages. The role of CoP in the context of the project may be summed up as follows:

- **Provide relevant information to the BioGov.net consortium** by participating (based on voluntary) in training events/workshops of the project, involve on related discussions, share knowledge, exchange experience (peer to peer dialog) on good practices, the results of which will procure a basis for the fine-tuning, roll-out and replication of the BioGov.net training framework.
- **Support the network for bio-based stakeholders** in the transition towards bioeconomy and identifying key elements.
- **Provide case studies** by participating in discussions about training, and retraining availabilities in the region, by identifying the skills gabs and policies' limitation.

To fulfil this role, it is envisaged that local CoPs, during the project, will operate through physical and digital means in the project activities. The main outcome of CoPs is to offer feedback loop from the society to the policy makers using the inclusive methods as designathons, co-design, policy bio-based workshops, and best practice guidelines for local operators and innovation developers and interact, if necessary, in multi stakeholders' consultation.

Benefits

The project **provides several benefits** to its CoP's members, such as:

- **Networking opportunities and possibilities for new collaborations** arising from the participation in project events and workshops.
- **First-hand access to meaningful insights, knowledge and practical tools** generated exclusively within the context of the project and its activities.
- Unique opportunity to **align the services offered by the BioGov.net guidelines and training framework with the needs of their stakeholders** to ensure that they make the most out of its value propositions.
- **Wider understanding of biosystems** and key enablers in bioeconomy as balanced local potentials and innovation within the framework of local development and investment as well as national sustainability-driven policy
- **Gain adequate information** and guidelines that respond to the need of bio-systems in each region and contribute to the transition to bioeconomy.
- Develop **exchanges within strategic alliances** and skills leading to novel business models or novel job descriptions.

Terms of membership and Management

Terms of membership

CoPs shall be composed of individuals coming from diverse backgrounds to offer a blend of expertise and perspectives that represent various stakeholder groups from the bioeconomy sector (such as, higher educational organizations and researchers, vocational educational organizations, bio systems stakeholders, SMEs, public authorities, policy makers, NGOs etc.). These individuals will provide BioGov.net with valuable knowledge and feedback to support the project's vision of training guidelines and the implementation of collaboratively developed results. Along these lines, at the beginning of the project, approximately 30 members in each country/local CoP will be selected to draw from additional expertise and increase the outreach of BioGov.net. New members could be appointed to the CoP when necessary and as the project evolves.

Although members of the CoP may be selected because of their affiliations with key organizations, they serve on the CoP in their **individual capacity** to represent the interests and views of their stakeholder communities. Members of the CoP are appointed for the entire duration of the project's CoP (from March 2023 to 31 May 2025). If for any reason a CoP member wants to step back from his/her role, the CoP Leader should be informed and – if possible – another expert may be suggested as replacement to carry out the role expected.

Participation in the CoP is **entirely voluntary**. There will be no adverse consequences if a CoP member decides not to participate or to withdraw at any stage. In fact, CoP members may withdraw their participation at any time by informing the Cop Leader, in terms of good communication and mutual positive attitude. They may also request their data to be withdrawn without giving a reason and without prejudice. Anonymous data already collected may be used because this information cannot be traced back to a specific person, but no further data or input will be collected, nor any other procedure will be carried out in relation to the specific member.

Management

Each local CoP is managed by the CoP Leader who handles communications and interactions with the Cop. The Leader will also ensure that for each task requiring input from the CoP, an action plan and all necessary briefings and material have been prepared beforehand.

Contact point

Any enquiry, complaint, or concern about any aspect of the experience as a member of the Community of Practices can be addressed to the **CoP Leader** that oversees the set up and manages the <country/region name> Community of Practice. The contact details of the Regional CoP Leader are provided below:

CoP Leader: <name of organisation serving as Leader>

Contact person: <name of person in charge for the CoP within the organisation>

Phone: <phone number of person in charge for the CoP within the organisation>

Email: <email of person in charge for the CoP within the organisation>

Annex III – Declaration of Acceptance for CoP Members

Declaration of Acceptance

(For individuals appointed as members of the BioGov.net Greek Community of Practice in their individual capacity)

I, the undersigned, _____ certify that I have read and agree to abide by the BioGov.net Community of Practice Terms of Reference.

I agree to participate in the BioGov.net Community of Practice in <region/country name> in my individual capacity and as such I may not delegate another person to carry out the work. If for any reason, I may want to step back from my role, the CoP Leader should be informed and – if possible – another expert may be suggested as replacement to carry out the role expected.

I certify that no conflict of interests exists that could be considered as prejudicial to my independence in acting as a member of the BioGov.net Community of Practice in <region/country name>.

I undertake not to divulge any information given in the context of the work of the <region/country name> Community of Practice, unless the BioGov.net consortium agrees to release me from this obligation, and to respect the confidentiality requirements.

I declare to accept entirely and with no reservations my appointment as BioGov.net Community of Practice member as described in the Terms of Reference.

I consent that any input or contribution I provide as member of the BioGov.net Community of Practice may be used by the BioGov.net consortium for reporting purposes or to align the services and tools offered by BioGov.net with the needs of final users to ensure that they make the most out of its value propositions.

I consent to the processing of my personal data needed for my participation in the BioGov.net Community of Practice. A detailed description on how BioGov.net handles personal data is presented in the project's Privacy Policy available through the project's web page at biogov.net

Name and Surname:

Place:

Date:

Signature:

Annex IV – Memorandum of Cooperation

MEMORANDUM OF COOPERATION

between

_____ [PARTNER NAME X] _____, called as CoP Leader in <region/country name>.

and

_____ [name of organisation Y] _____, called as Member of CoP

on

Community of Practice (CoP), BioGov.net project (GA Number 101060742).

BioGov.net Community of Practice (CoP) is conceived as a setup of 8 local Communities of Practice (in 8 different countries/region) that bring together various local stakeholders: research and education organisations, policy and decision makers, industries and businesses, citizens, NGOs etc. BioGov.net applies a multi-stakeholder approach by bringing together the different stakeholder groups, by strengthening already existing educational networks (actors involved in adult learning, retraining and skills' development) and initiatives with pioneers in the field.

I. Subject of the Memorandum

1. The subject of this memorandum is the commitment of the involved parties to be part of the <country/region name> Community of Practice (CoP) of BioGov.net project, as an important member of the bioeconomy stakeholder system and local resources within each country, selected to establish innovative governance models in bioeconomy and thus to support better-informed decision-making processes, social engagement between actors and sustainable innovations in bioeconomy.

II. Rights and obligations of the Involved parties

1. A member of the <country/region name> Community of Practice (CoP) has the right to be presented on the website of the BioGov.net at the domain www.biogov.net which is managed by the BioGov.net Dissemination and Communication Manager (GLOBAZ SA). The scope of the data published on the website of <country/region name> Community of Practice (CoP) is determined by the Member of <country/region name> Community of Practice (CoP), who by signing this Memorandum expresses his consent to their publication.

2. A member of Community of Practice (CoP) has the right to a presentation within the database of stakeholders created in the context of the BioGov.net project. The scope of data and consent to publication is regulated separately in the context of a signed Informed Consent Form.

3. A member of the <country/region name> Community of Practice (CoP) has the right to use the logo of BioGov.net and other elements of the project identity. Member of the <country/region name> Community of Practice (CoP) has the obligation to comply with the rules set out in the BioGov.net Dissemination and Communication Plan in particular not to use the logo in situations leading to the dishonour of BioGov.net, activities that contradict the principles of the bioeconomy, sound management of the project and partners' acceptance.

III. Final Provisions

1. The involved parties undertake to develop activities related to the achievement of the purpose of this memorandum and bear full responsibility for the implementation of activities and the fulfillment of the resulting obligations from I. and II. this contract.
2. Each of the involved parties is obliged to refrain from any activity that could make it impossible or difficult achieving the purpose of this memorandum. Furthermore, each of the involved parties is obliged to refrain from any actions that could endanger the interests of other involved parties in connection with the achievement of the purpose of this memorandum.
3. The involved parties are obliged to act ethically, correctly, and transparently during the implementation of the Project and in accordance with good manners.
4. The signatories of this memorandum express their willingness to cooperate with each other in the areas defined herein by memorandum in the forms indicated here.
5. The memorandum is an expression of the free will of its signatories.
6. This memorandum can only be changed and supplemented by accepted written amendments and signed by all signatories.
7. The memorandum is drawn up in two copies, with each signatory receiving one copy.

This memorandum of cooperation is entered into force

On the ____ day of ____ in the year ____.

.....
CoP Leader

.....
Member of CoP

Annex V – Informed Consent Form for CoP members

Informed Consent Form

Who we are:

We are an innovation consulting company named [name of partner] and we are contacting you in the framework of BioGov.net, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description on how BioGov.net handles personal data is presented in the project’s Privacy Policy that accompanies this Consent Form, also available through the project’s web site www.biogov.net. Apart from this, [name of partner] has issued its own Privacy Policy available here [please insert a link if exists].

Project:

BioGov.net – Mobilizing European Communities of Practice in bio-based systems for better governance and skills development networks in bioeconomy (GA Number 101060742).

Partner:

Organisation name:

Address:

Phone: / **E-mail:**

Responsible persons:

Table 1 Responsible Persons

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1	BioGov.net Project Manager/ Community of Practice Leader	xxx	xxx
2	Data Protection Officer	xxx	xxx
3	Contact Person	xxx	xxx

What do we need from you?

We need you to participate in the BioGov.net Community of Practice (CoP) with a view to participate in project activities including events, workshops, focus groups and interviews and provide your views and feedback to validated guidelines for set up of the regional bioeconomy training and mentoring framework.

To effectively carry out the activities of the Community of Practice, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Your contact details (full name, email, phone number);
- Some basic demographics (age, gender);
- Your professional info (organization, job position, field of expertise);
- Your education info
- Your opinions on the subject matter(s) of relevant events.

Why do we need your data & what will we do with them?

We need your data to contact you in order to plan and carry out activities related to the CoP and to resolve any ambiguities, questions and other issues that may arise after and as a result of your participation in such activities. We will keep your data to keep track of the implementation of the activities. The project's deliverables that will be derived by activities in which you participate will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you.

We are obliged and may grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation.
- EU agencies and other authorities for project's auditing purposes.

We would also be very happy if you gave us your consent to contact you in the future to ask you to participate in other project activities (e.g., surveys, interviews, project events etc.) and also to inform you about the project's progress (e.g. by sending you a newsletter or similar messages).

Furthermore, as we consider you to be a key stakeholder in the bioeconomy sector, we would like to form a stronger bond with you, so we ask for your consent to contact you for participating in similar projects that we may undertake in the future.

How can you withdraw your consent?

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating either on the phone or by email with the responsible persons listed in the previous page. With regards to the informational messages and newsletters you can always opt out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

*(Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that **you do not consent to the relevant subject.**)*

Table 2. Consent details

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in the CoP and its related activities with a view to support research activities of the project, as well as the development and validation of bioeconomy training and mentoring BioGov.net guidelines.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	My participation in regional Innovation Group. (Innovation Groups connect the most influential players in transition to Bioeconomy)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	My participation in future activities of BioGov.net	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Receiving newsletters and messages regarding BioGov.net activities	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	My participation in similar projects that name of partner may undertake in the future	<input type="checkbox"/>

 Name of participant

 Date

 Signature

Annex VI – Stakeholder
 Matrix Template

Internal Stakeholder Matrix																
Demographics					Project Activities											
Organization name	Type	Contact person	Address of organization	Phone Number of contact person	Email address of contact person	Region	Country	Age	Gender	Regional Interviews for good practices and success case studies (WP2, T2.2)	Regional Designathon Alternatively Focus Group & Co-creation Workshops (WP3, T3.2.1)	Regional Co-Design Workshops (WP3, T3.2.2)	Regional Policy Workshops (WP3, T3.2.3)	Focus Groups (WP5, T5.1)	Mutual Learning, Co-Creation workshop (WP5, T5.2.1)	Workshop in framework of EU (WP5, T5.2.2)

Consortium

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